

RESEARCH ARTICLE

REVISÉD Awareness and Acceptability of Prenatal Diagnosis of Sickle Cell Disease among Mothers of Affected Children in a Northern Nigerian Teaching Hospital

[version 2; peer review: 2 approved, 1 approved with reservations]

Aliyu RM^{1,2}, Sada SI ^{1,2}, Adebisi NM ³, Randawa AJ^{1,2}, Abdulkadir I^{3,4}, Ahmad HR ^{3,4}

¹Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Ahmadu Bello University Faculty of Medicine, Zaria, Kaduna, Nigeria

²Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital, Zaria, Kaduna, Nigeria

³Department of Paediatrics, Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital, Zaria, Kaduna, Nigeria

⁴Department of Paediatrics, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Kaduna, Nigeria

v2 First published: 10 Sep 2025, 5:278
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18700.1>
 Latest published: 09 Dec 2025, 5:278
<https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18700.2>

Abstract

Background

Nigeria has the highest global prevalence of sickle cell disease (SCD), necessitating effective preventive measures to control the disease. Prenatal diagnosis (PND) is a key early intervention for SCD, yet there is a shortage of studies in Northern Nigeria focusing on mothers of children with SCD. These mothers not only carry the burden of the disease but also face the risk of having more affected children, making them vital stakeholders in managing and controlling SCD. This study assessed the awareness and acceptability of prenatal diagnosis PND for SCD among mothers of children with the disease.

Methods

A cross-sectional study was conducted involving 297 mothers of children with SCD attending the Paediatric Haematology clinic at Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital, Zaria, Nigeria. Data were collected via an interviewer-administered questionnaire addressing the characteristics of the children and mothers, as well as their awareness, attitudes, and acceptability of PND. SPSS version 23 was used for data analysis, with a p-value < 0.05 considered statistically significant.

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

	1	2	3
version 2 (revision) 09 Dec 2025			 view
version 1 10 Sep 2025	 view	 view	

1. **Lori C Jordan** , Vanderbilt University Medical Center, Nashville, USA
2. **Vincenzo Voi** , University of Turin, Turin, Italy
3. **Aisha Galandanci**, St Jude Children's Research Hospital, Memphis, USA
Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital (Ringgold ID: 376586), Kano, Nigeria

Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

Results

Most participants (90.9%) were of Hausa ethnicity and 97.0% were of Islamic faith. A majority (77.8%) had less than tertiary education, and 57.9% lacked personal income. Nearly 41% had more than one child affected by SCD, and about one-fifth had lost a child to SCD complications. Only 22.2% of mothers had heard of PND, mostly from healthcare workers, and just 0.3% had undergone the procedure. After receiving information about PND, 93.3% were willing to accept it, though 45% of those who declined cited religious beliefs. Factors associated with PND acceptance included the mother's education and the child's SCD severity.

Conclusion

Awareness of PND among at-risk mothers is low, yet most expressed willingness to accept it. Educational level and disease severity were associated with PND acceptability.

Plain language summary

Nigeria has the highest number of people with sickle cell disease (SCD) in the world. To help prevent more children from being born with the disease, prenatal diagnosis (PND) allows parents to know whether their baby will have SCD before birth. However, there is little research in Northern Nigeria focusing on mothers who already have children with SCD. These mothers carry the heavy burden of caring for sick children and face the possibility of having more children with the disease. Understanding how much these mothers know about PND and whether they would be willing to use it is important for controlling the spread of SCD. In this study, 297 mothers of children with SCD attending a hospital in Zaria, Nigeria, were surveyed. The mothers answered questions about their children, personal background, and knowledge of and willingness to accept PND. The data were analyzed to identify factors that influenced awareness and acceptability of PND. The majority of the mothers were Hausa and Muslim, and most had low levels of education. Over half of the mothers had no personal income. Nearly 41% of the mothers had more than one child with SCD, and about 20% had lost a child due to the disease. Only 22.2% of the mothers had heard of PND, mostly from healthcare workers, and just 0.3% had undergone the procedure. After learning more about PND, 93.3% of the mothers said they would be willing to use it. However, religious belief was the main reason for refusal among those who declined. Mothers with higher education levels and those whose children had more severe disease manifestation were more likely to accept PND. In conclusion, awareness of PND among these mothers is low, but most are open to it once informed. Educational efforts could improve acceptance of PND in Northern Nigeria.

Keywords

awareness, acceptability, prenatal diagnosis, mothers, sickle cell disease.

This article is included in the [Marie-Sklodowska-Curie Actions \(MSCA\)](#) gateway.

This article is included in the [Horizon 2020](#) gateway.

This article is included in the [Health Sciences](#) gateway.

Corresponding author: Aliyu RM (rmaliyu@abu.edu.ng)

Author roles: **RM A:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **SI S:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **NM A:** Conceptualization, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **AJ R:** Conceptualization, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **I A:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing; **HR A:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – Original Draft Preparation, Writing – Review & Editing

Competing interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Grant information: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No [GA 824021 — ARISE — H2020-MSCA-ARISE-2018]. The authors declare that there was no financial grant directly involved in supporting this work."

Copyright: © 2025 RM A *et al.* This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

How to cite this article: RM A, SI S, NM A *et al.* **Awareness and Acceptability of Prenatal Diagnosis of Sickle Cell Disease among Mothers of Affected Children in a Northern Nigerian Teaching Hospital [version 2; peer review: 2 approved, 1 approved with reservations]** Open Research Europe 2025, 5:278 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18700.2>

First published: 10 Sep 2025, 5:278 <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18700.1>

REVISED Amendments from Version 1

This version addressed a few comments raised by the reviewer. These include the number of children with SCD seen in the paediatric haematology clinic; description of the terms grandmultipara and tertiary education; the place of premarital screening as an alternative to prenatal diagnosis in SCD control and the role of religion leaders in implementation of control measures for SCD.

Any further responses from the reviewers can be found at the end of the article

Introduction

Sickle cell disease (SCD) is the most common hemoglobinopathy in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) with Nigeria having the highest prevalence globally^{1,2}. The World Health Organisation (WHO) has identified SCD as a public health burden due to its high morbidity and mortality rates. In SSA, most affected children die before their fifth birthday, and survivors face recurrent episodes of anemia, blood transfusions, crises, and repeated hospital admissions. These not only cause physical ill-health but also lead to significant psychosocial trauma for affected individuals and their families, creating a substantial socio-economic burden on families, society, and the country³. Therefore, preventing SCD is essential to reduce its overall burden.

Early diagnosis of SCD is a key strategy in controlling the disease, as it allows for the timely implementation of appropriate and acceptable measures. Screening for SCD can occur at various stages of life, with prenatal diagnosis (PND) being one of the earliest available options. PND is performed during early pregnancy for couples at risk of having children with SCD. This diagnosis can be conducted using invasive tests, such as chorionic villus sampling or amniocentesis, and more recently, a non-invasive technique has been developed. The non-invasive prenatal test screens for fetal SCD using cell-free fetal DNA from maternal plasma, eliminating the risk of miscarriage associated with invasive tests^{3,4}. This method also allows for earlier screening than conventional invasive tests.

There is a scarcity of centers offering PND in Nigeria, and its acceptability is often influenced by religious beliefs⁵. The benefits of PND include early detection of abnormalities in the fetus, allowing a couple time to prepare psychologically, socially, and financially for the birth of an affected child if they choose to continue the pregnancy. It also provides the option to terminate the pregnancy if the birth of an affected child is not desired, in situations where pregnancy termination is acceptable and permissible. Additionally, PND can relieve anxiety early in pregnancy if the disease is excluded.

Although some studies have been conducted on the knowledge and acceptability of PND of SCD in the general population, there is a lack of research in Northern Nigeria focusing on mothers of children with SCD. These mothers are already carrying the burden of the disease, are at risk of having another affected child, and are important stakeholders in SCD control. This study aims to assess the awareness and acceptability of PND of SCD among mothers of children with SCD.

Methods**Study setting**

The study was conducted in the Paediatric Haematology clinic of Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital, Zaria, which operates weekly on Wednesdays. The clinic sees an average of 50 children with SCD each week.

Study design

This was a cross-sectional descriptive study.

Study population

The study population included mothers of children with SCD who were attending the clinic.

Inclusion criteria

All consenting mothers of at least one child living with sickle cell disease were included in the study.

Exclusion criteria

Exclusion criteria were menopausal mothers, mothers who had undergone bilateral tubal ligation, and mothers whose current spouse had an Hb genotype of AA.

Sample size determination

Using a prevalence of awareness of 0.25% among mothers of affected children as reported by Olatunya⁶, where n = sample size; Z = standard normal variate (1.96 at $P < 0.05$); p = percentage of awareness of prenatal diagnosis (0.25); q = $1 - p$ (0.75), d = absolute precision (0.05), a minimum sample size of 288 was obtained. However, 297 women were recruited for the study.

Sampling technique

A non-probability sampling method was used to sequentially recruit eligible mothers of affected children from the clinic as they presented to access care until the desired sample size was achieved. Recruitment took place from March to August, 2023.

Study protocol

Every eligible participant completed a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire, after obtaining informed verbal consent, to gather data on socio-demographic characteristics, awareness, attitude, and acceptability of prenatal diagnosis for SCD. None of the eligible participants declined participation. The data collected was pseudo-anonymized. Recruitment took place from March to August 2023.

Data analysis

Data were analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (IBM SPSS statistics) version 23⁶. The level of significance was set at < 0.05 . Frequencies and percentages were used to describe categorical data, and Chi-square/Fisher's exact test was used to test for associations between variables.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval (ABUTHZ/HREC/H32/2022) was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of ABUTH, Zaria, on 14 September 2022. Participants were provided with adequate

information, and informed verbal consent was obtained from all the study participants before the questionnaires were administered. Verbal consent was used because it has been established in a national document that Kaduna state (where the study was conducted) has a low literacy level, with only 18% of the female population reported to have attained secondary or higher education (National Health Demographic Survey, 2018). The study also posed a no-minimal risk to the participants and the information collected was de-identified. The scope of the study and process involved was discussed with each participant. The participant was allowed the opportunity to ask questions and her concerns addressed if any before giving consent. The questionnaires were de-identified, and confidentiality was strictly maintained. Collected hard copy data was securely stored, and only the principal investigator had access to the input data on a computer.

Results

A total of 297 mothers of children with SCD were recruited. The majority of the mothers (90.9%) were of Hausa ethnicity, 97.0% were of Islamic faith, 77.8% had below tertiary education, and 57.9% had no source of personal income. About one-third of the mothers were grandmultiparous women (≥ 5 deliveries). Additionally, 40.7% had more than one child affected by SCD, and about one-fifth had experienced the loss of at least one child due to SCD-related complications. Further details are provided in [Table 1](#).

Two-thirds of the affected children were aged five years or younger. The predominant hemoglobin genotype among the children was Hb SS (99%). Approximately half of the children experienced at least one crisis per month. In the past year, 55.2% of the children were hospitalized, and 44.4% received blood transfusions due to SCD-related complications. Detailed

characteristics of the affected children attending the SCD clinic are provided in [Table 2](#).

Only 22.2% of the mothers (66 out of 297) had ever heard of PND for SCD. The most common source of information about PND was healthcare workers, while the least common source was electronic media. This is illustrated in [Figure 1](#).

The majority of the mothers (44 out of 66) were unaware of the methods that can be used for PND. Among those who were aware, chorionic villus sampling or amniocentesis was the most commonly known method (14 out of 66). Only 13.6% (9 out of 66) of the mothers knew more than one method of PND. These findings are depicted in [Figure 2](#).

Only one mother (0.3%) had ever undergone a form of PND of SCD. However, when informed about PND of SCD, 93.3% of the mothers expressed willingness to accept the test. Among those who were not willing to accept PND, 45% were willing to accept the fate of having another child with SCD. These findings are detailed in [Table 3](#).

Mother's educational level, having a child experiencing at least one crisis per month, and receiving at least one blood transfusion or hospital admission in the past year were significantly associated with willingness to accept PND for SCD ($p < 0.05$). These associations are presented in [Table 4](#).

Discussion

The global number of people with sickle cell disease (SCD) has increased by 41.4% over the past 21 years⁷. The birth prevalence of SCD among children under one-year-old is reported to be highest in Africa, ranging from 643 to 2800 per 100,000, with particularly high mortality rates⁸. This highlights the urgent need

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of mothers of children with SCD.

Characteristic	Frequency (%)	Characteristic	Frequency (%)
Tribe		Religion	
Hausa	270 (90.9)	Islam	288 (97.0)
Non-Hausa	27 (9.1)	Christianity	9 (3.0)
Educational level		Parity	
Below tertiary	231 (77.8)	<5	186 (62.6)
Tertiary*	66 (22.2)	≥ 5	111 (37.4)
Residence		No. of children with SCD	
Rural	79 (26.6)	1	176 (59.3)
Semi-urban/urban	218 (73.4)	≥ 1	121 (40.7)
Personal source of income		No. of sickle cell related deaths	
Yes	125 (42.1)	0	235 (79.1)
No	172 (57.9)	≥ 1	62 (20.9)

*Tertiary: additional education beyond secondary level such as diplomas, degrees, postgraduate.

Table 2. Characteristics of the affected children attending the SCD clinic.

Characteristic	Frequency (%)
Age (years)	
≤5	197 (66.3)
>5	100 (33.7)
Haemoglobin genotype	
SS	294 (99.0)
SC	3 (1.0)
Average crisis per month	
0	146 (49.2)
≥1	151 (50.8)
SCD-related blood transfusion in the last one year	
0	165 (55.6)
≥1	132 (44.4)
SCD-related hospital admission in the last one year	
0	133 (44.8)
≥1	164 (55.2)

for effective SCD control measures in SSA to reduce associated morbidity and mortality. PND is one of the reproductive options available to couples at high risk of transmitting a serious genetic disorder. Awareness and utilization of PND have increased in developed countries, where it is routinely offered as part of informed reproductive choices, but remains low in Africa, which carries the highest burden of the disease⁹.

This study found a low level of awareness of PND for SCD, which aligns with findings by Olutanya *et al.* in Southwestern Nigeria¹⁰. Similarly, Munung *et al.* in a multi-country study of people directly affected by SCD, reported a low level of awareness of PND¹¹. This low level of awareness mirrors the general awareness of prenatal diagnosis for other genetic conditions in various study populations, such as pregnant women¹²⁻¹⁴. The widespread poor awareness of PND for genetic disorders could be attributed to a lack of facilities and expertise for PND in

Figure 1. Sources of information about PND for SCD among mothers of affected children. The colours represent the different sources of information about PND.

Figure 2. Awareness of PND methods among mothers of children with SCD. The bars represent the methods of SCD PND known to the participants.

Table 3. Acceptability of PND for SCD among mothers.

Variable	Frequency (%) n=297
Ever had PND for SCD	
Yes	1 (0.3)
No	298 (99.7)
Willingness to accept PND in the future	n=297
Yes	277 (93.3)
No	20 (6.7)
Reasons for unwillingness to accept PND in the future	n=20
I will accept my fate	9 (45.0)
No reason stated	11 (55.0)

Nigeria and the reluctance of some healthcare workers to recommend PND for SCD. A study among physicians found that nearly two-thirds would not recommend PND for at-risk couples¹⁰. This also highlights the low uptake of PND for SCD in this study, with only one mother having undergone PND in a previous pregnancy, as reported in a similar study in Nigeria¹⁴. In contrast, Okechukwu *et al.* found higher awareness of PND (52.2%) among parents of SCD children in South-South Nigeria¹⁵.

In this study, the internet and social media were not major sources of information about PND for SCD. In the digital era, this emphasizes the need for organisations responsible for SCD control to utilise these media to disseminate accurate and easily understandable information.

Following information on PND for SCD provided to participants in this study, the majority expressed a willingness to accept PND, consistent with reports by Ampumah *et al.* from Ghana and Wonkam *et al.* from Cameroon^{16,17}. However, Olatunya *et al.* and Okechukwu reported lower acceptability rates in similar

Table 4. Factors associated with the willingness to accept PND for SCD in future pregnancies.

Factor	Frequency (%) n=297		p-value
	Will accept PND	Will not accept PND	
Educational level			
Tertiary	57	9	0.011
Below tertiary	220	11	
Personal source of income			
Yes	116	9	0.785
No	161	11	
Place of residence			
Semi-urban/urban	202	16	0.489
Rural	75	4	
No. of SCD-related death			
≥1	57	5	0.638
0	220	15	
Average crisis per month			
≥1	147	4	0.005
0	130	16	
SCD-related blood transfusion in the last one year			
≥1	128	4	0.034
0	149	16	

Factor	Frequency (%) n=297		p-value
	Will accept PND	Will not accept PND	
SCD-related hospital admission in the last one year			
≥1	161	3	0.000
0	116	17	
No. of children affected with SCD			
≥2	167	9	0.158
1	110	11	

populations¹⁵. This could be due to differences in the intrinsic characteristics of the study populations. In the study by Olatunya, 97% of participants had only one affected child, whereas more than half of the mothers in this study had more than one affected child. Additionally, mothers in this study had experienced SCD-related deaths five times more frequently than participants in Okechukwu's study. Caring for a person with SCD carries a significant psychological, financial, and physical burden¹⁸. This burden is even greater when more than one child in a family is affected by SCD, which may influence mothers' attitudes toward the acceptability of PND for SCD.

In this study, nearly half of the mothers who were unwilling to accept PND cited a willingness to accept the risk of having another affected child. Acceptance of one's fate is closely associated with religious belief, similar to findings from southern Nigeria¹⁵. Religion is a strong factor in the decision-making process for prenatal screening¹⁹. This study found that severe manifestations of the disease evident by frequent crises, blood transfusions, and hospital admissions were associated with willingness to accept PND. The psychosocial burden faced by these mothers of affected children does not exist in other studied populations, such as healthcare providers or students²⁰. Cultural, religious, and personal concerns about pregnancy termination are factors associated with willingness to accept PND for SCD^{11,19}. Ampumah *et al.* in Ghana reported that parents of children living with SCD were more likely to use PND results to prepare for the birth of the child, and deciding to accept PND did not necessarily mean using that information to terminate the pregnancy¹⁶. Munung *et al.* in Ghana found a lower preference for PND as a SCD control measure largely due to its complex decision-making process and higher risk of stigmatization which are influenced by religious and cultural aspects attached to the termination of an affected pregnancy that can follow a PND¹¹. In a resource-poor country where the resources to establish widespread PND is lacking; a populace whom cultural and religious beliefs influence their decision making; a restrictive abortion law and high burden of SCD-related morbidity and mortality, there is need to strengthen other less expensive control measures in the countries like premarital/premarital counseling and testing and newborn screening. In the Nigerian setting, awareness and acceptance of premarital screening for SCD are already relatively high²¹, and studies have shown that many African individuals hold positive attitudes toward genetic counselling²². Evidence from a multi-African country study by

Munung *et al.* further suggests that adolescents may be an ideal target group for early sickle cell trait screening, given their openness to receiving genetic information before marriage decisions are made¹¹. This indicates a valuable opportunity to expand low-cost control measures. In contexts where religious leaders play a central role in guiding social and marital decisions, their involvement could significantly enhance the uptake and acceptability of other control measures like premarital screening. Engaging community faith structures—for example, offering voluntary carrier testing through local mosques or churches—may be culturally appropriate and effective. Religious leaders often hold strong influence and have been shown to express supportive attitudes toward premarital SCD screening, and they could play a constructive role in communicating the health implications of two carriers marrying²³. Cell-free fetal DNA testing in maternal serum is currently unavailable in Kaduna, and only a few centres offer the service nationwide, at prohibitively high costs.

Educational level was the only socio-demographic variable of mothers associated with willingness to accept PND, similar to findings by Mattei *et al.* in a recent systematic review²⁴. Other studies have also reported that educational level is generally associated with willingness to accept PND, not just for SCD^{25,26}.

This study derives its strengths from the use of a large sample size; use of a relevant target population of women with a strong stake in control measures of SCD like PND; provides valuable insights into public health strategies and interventions in the control of SCD in a country with the highest burden of SCD and thus could inform future research and policy.

Limitations of this study include the use of a convenience sampling method as it does not randomly select mothers from the target population; reliance on self-reported data where the respondents may not truly reveal their beliefs and attitudes and being a single-centred study where the respondents were Muslims and of Hausa ethnicity which could limit diversity of perspectives represented in this study.

Conclusion

Only one-fifth of at-risk mothers were aware of PND as a control measure for SCD, and actual use of PND was very low. Most mothers expressed a willingness to accept PND and religious belief was the main reason for declining PND. Mother's

educational status and the severity of the child's disease were associated with a willingness to accept PND.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval (ABUTHZ/HREC/H32/2022) was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of ABUTH, Zaria, on 14 September 2022. Participants were provided with adequate information, and informed verbal consent was obtained from all the study participants before the questionnaires were administered. Verbal consent was used because it has been established in a national document that Kaduna state (where the study was conducted) has a low literacy level, with only 18% of the female population reported to have attained secondary or higher education (National Health Demographic Survey, 2018). The study also posed a no-minimal risk to the participants and the information collected was de-identified. The scope of the study and process involved was discussed with each participant. The participant was allowed the opportunity to ask questions and her concerns addressed if any before giving consent. The questionnaires were de-identified, and confidentiality was strictly

maintained. Collected hard copy data was securely stored, and only the principal investigator had access to the input data on a computer.

Data availability statement

The data underlying this article are openly available in the Figshare repository under a CC BY 4.0. The dataset can be accessed via the following DOI [10.6084/m9.figshare.27195288](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.27195288)⁶.

Data are available under the terms of the CC BY 4.0

Acknowledgement

All the activities related to this research have been performed in compliance with the applicable national/local rules and respecting participants' rights. The training on methodology/data analysis/publication drafting was received in the framework of the African Research Innovative Initiative on Sickle Cell Education project (GA 824021 — ARISE — H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018).

References

- Regional Committee for Africa: **Sickle-Cell Disease: a strategy for the WHO African region**. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2011. [Reference Source](#)
- Federal Ministry of Health: **National guideline for control and management of Sickle Cell Disease**. Abuja: Federal Ministry of Health, 2014. [Reference Source](#)
- Grosse SD, Odame I, Atrash HK, *et al.*: **Sickle Cell Disease in Africa: a neglected cause of early childhood mortality**. *Am J Prev Med*. 2011; **41**(6 Suppl 4): S398–405. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Kato GJ, Piel FB, Reid CD, *et al.*: **Sickle Cell Disease**. *Nat Rev Dis Prim*. 2018; **4**: 18010. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ojewunmi OO, Adeyemo TA, Ayinde OC, *et al.*: **Current perspectives of Sickle Cell Disease in Nigeria: changing the narratives**. *Expert Rev Hematol*. 2019; **12**(8): 609–620. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Aliyu RM, Adebisi NM, Sada SI, *et al.*: **Awareness and acceptability of prenatal diagnosis of Sickle Cell Disease among mothers of affected children in a Northern Nigerian Teaching Hospital**. [Dataset], Figshare. 2024. <http://www.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.27195288>
- GBD 2021 Sickle Cell Disease Collaborators: **Global, regional, and national prevalence and mortality burden of Sickle Cell Disease, 2000–2021: a systematic analysis from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2021**. *Lancet Haematol*. 2023; **10**(8): e585–e599. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Colombatti R, Hegemann I, Medici M, *et al.*: **Correction: Colombatti et al. Systematic Literature Review Shows Gaps in Data on Global Prevalence and Birth Prevalence of Sickle Cell Disease and Sickle Cell Trait: Call for Action to Scale Up and Harmonize Data Collection**. *J. Clin. Med*. 2023, **12**, 5538. *J Clin Med*. 2024; **13**(10):2893. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Nzekwue C, Ogueh O: **Prenatal diagnosis and preimplantation genetic diagnosis for Sickle Cell Disease in Africa**. *J Glob Med*. 2022; **2**(1): e75. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Olatunya OS, Babatola AO, Ogundare EO, *et al.*: **Perceptions and practice of early diagnosis of Sickle Cell Disease by parents and physicians in a Southwestern state of Nigeria**. *Sci World J*. 2020; **2020**: 4801087. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Munung NS, Kamga KK, Treadwell MJ, *et al.*: **Perceptions and preferences for genetic testing for Sickle Cell Disease or trait: a qualitative study in Cameroon, Ghana and Tanzania**. *Eur J Hum Genet*. 2024; **32**(10): 1307–1313. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Ahmed Y, Panti AA, Umar A, *et al.*: **Knowledge and acceptability of prenatal diagnosis among pregnant women attending antenatal clinic in a tertiary health institution in Sokoto, Nigeria**. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol*. 2021; **10**(12): 3678–84. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ogamba CF, Babah OA, Roberts AA, *et al.*: **Knowledge, attitudes, and decision making towards prenatal testing among antenatal clinic attendees in Lagos University Teaching Hospital: an institution-based cross-sectional study**. *Pan Afr Med J*. 2021; **39**: 106. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Adenmosun O, Andrew M, Taiwo O, *et al.*: **Knowledge and perception of pregnant women on control measures for sickle cell disorder in South-Western Nigeria**. *Int J Med Sci Health Res*. 2018; **2**(2): 200–12. [Reference Source](#)
- Okechukwu C: **Prenatal diagnosis in Sickle Cell Disease: in the eyes of the couple at risk**. *J Adv Med Med Res*. 2020; **32**(10): 65–71. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ampomah MO, Atkin K, Flemming K: **The perception of parents with a child with Sickle Cell Disease in Ghana towards prenatal diagnosis**. *J Community Genet*. 2022; **13**(6): 587–95. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
- Wonkam A, Njamnshi AK, Mbanya D, *et al.*: **Acceptability of prenatal diagnosis by a sample of parents of sickle cell anemia patients in cameroon (sub-Saharan Africa)**. *J Genet Couns*. 2011; **20**(5): 476–85. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Beli II, Ali LA, Onuoha CC, *et al.*: **Socio-economic burden of Sickle Cell Disease on families attending sickle cell clinic in Kano State, Northwestern Nigeria**. *Glob Pediatr Health*. 2024; **9**: 100193. [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ahmed S, Atkin K, Hewison J, *et al.*: **The influence of faith and religion and the role of religious and community leaders in prenatal decisions for sickle cell disorders and thalassaemia major**. *Prenat Diagn*. 2006; **26**(9): 801–9. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Animasahun BA, Nwodo U, Njokanma OF: **Prenatal screening for sickle cell anemia: awareness among health professionals and medical students at the Lagos University Teaching Hospital and the concept of prevention by termination**. *J Pediatr Hematol Oncol*. 2012; **34**(4): 252–6. [PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#)
- Ugwu NI: **Pre-marital screening for sickle cell haemoglobin and genetic counseling: awareness and acceptability among undergraduate students**

- of a Nigerian university. *Int J Med Biomed Res.* 2016; **5**(1): 43–49.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
22. Akinola A, Kaushik M, Constance MS: **Sickle Cell Disease knowledge and attitude towards premarital genetic counselling of African students in Africa: a systematic review.** *IJRAR.* 2020; **7**(3).
23. Abubakar SB, Abdulqadir I, Magaji BA, *et al.*: **Knowledge, attitude and perception of traditional and religious leaders on pre-marital screening for Sickle Cell Disease in Sokoto.** *Int J Med Public Health.* 2019; **9**(2): 36–41.
[Publisher Full Text](#)
24. Di Mattei V, Ferrari F, Perego G, *et al.*: **Decision-making factors in prenatal testing: a systematic review.** *Health Psychol Open.* 2021; **8**(1): 2055102920987455.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
25. Arumugam S, Kalluri SS, Sharmila V, *et al.*: **Acceptability of prenatal screening tests among expectant mothers in India: insights and implications for public health.** *Cureus.* 2024; **16**(5): e61246.
[PubMed Abstract](#) | [Publisher Full Text](#) | [Free Full Text](#)
26. Adekanbi AOA, Olayemi OO, Fawole AO: **The knowledge base and acceptability of prenatal diagnosis by pregnant women in Ibadan.** *Afr J Reprod Health.* 2014; **18**(1): 127–32.
[PubMed Abstract](#)

Open Peer Review

Current Peer Review Status:

Version 2

Reviewer Report 06 January 2026

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.23958.r65979>

© 2026 Galandanci A. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Aisha Galandanci

¹ Global Pediatric Medicine, St Jude Children's Research Hospital, Memphis, TN, USA

² Hematology, Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital (Ringgold ID: 376586), Kano, Kano, Nigeria

This study is particularly significant, especially as Nigeria bears the highest global burden of SCD. While the findings provide valuable insights into barriers to PND uptake, the absence of a discussion on the cost of PND relative to the mother's income is a notable limitation. In low-resource settings, out-of-pocket costs are often a major factor influencing healthcare decisions. It would be useful to explore whether lack of affordability or cost awareness may have contributed to the low acceptability rates observed.

The study could also benefit from addressing the limited autonomy many women experience in reproductive decision-making, particularly those with less formal education. In many Nigerian households, such decisions are made by husbands or extended family members, which may explain the reluctance to accept PND even when it is available.

In the discussion, the authors rightly note that in a resource-poor country where widespread access to PND is limited, and where cultural, religious, and legal factors influence decision-making, there is an urgent need to strengthen other cost-effective control measures such as premarital counseling, carrier testing, and newborn screening. Building on this, the manuscript could consider emphasizing collaboration with religious leaders to provide culturally sensitive education on SCD and Islamic perspectives on PND. Religious institutions such as mosques could play an important role in increasing awareness and trust. Similarly, expanding SCD education and screening awareness to universities and public institutions may help reach younger individuals before marriage or childbearing.

Finally, minor editorial revisions are recommended to improve clarity including removing redundant content (e.g., the repeated ethics section) and ensuring consistency in abbreviation usage (e.g., defining SCD once). These adjustments would enhance the manuscript's overall impact and readability.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: 1) Hemoglobinopathies, particularly Sickle Cell Disease (SCD), Epidemiology and disease burden, Newborn screening (NBS) for SCD, prevention strategies and genetic counseling, community health education and awareness, 2) Quantitative and qualitative research methods, caregiver experiences and health-seeking behavior, sociocultural and religious influences on health decisions,

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Version 1

Reviewer Report 25 November 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.20230.r63815>

© 2025 Voi V. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Vincenzo Voi

University of Turin, Turin, Italy

Peer Review Report – Open Research Europe

Title

Awareness and Acceptability of Prenatal Diagnosis of Sickle Cell Disease among Mothers of Affected Children in a Northern Nigerian Teaching Hospital

General Assessment

The manuscript addresses a highly relevant topic in the field of sickle cell disease (SCD) prevention. The study is clearly structured and uses a sample directly relevant to the research

question.

Some methodological and interpretative aspects require clarification:

Methods – Points Requiring Revision

Referenced text: “After obtaining informed verbal consent, every eligible participant completed a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire...”

Suggested revision: I agree with my previous colleague. The manuscript should report the number of mothers who declined participation. If none declined, authors should explicitly state this.

Moreover, clarification is needed on the total number of children with SCD routinely followed at the clinic to contextualize the recruitment proportion.

Results – Clarifications Needed

Referenced text: “About one-third of the mothers were grandmultiparous...”

Suggested revision: Define clearly what threshold the authors used for ‘grand multiparous’.

Literature definitions vary (≥ 5 deliveries is common).

Define the operational threshold used in this study to classify grand multiparity. In the narrative text, however, the authors describe the mothers as “about one-third grand multiparous” with a “median parity of 3,” which seems inconsistent with the ≥ 5 threshold reported in the table.

If the intended definition is ≥ 5 deliveries, adjust the text to align with the tables. If the authors used a different definition, modify the table labels accordingly.

Referenced text: “Below tertiary vs tertiary”

Suggested revision: Specify what is included under ‘tertiary education’. Indicate whether it reflects post-secondary, university-level, or vocational training.

Discussion – Conceptual Expansion Needed

Referenced text: “There is need to strengthen other less expensive control measures...”

Suggested revision: Expand this point. In regions where pregnancy termination is culturally or religiously restricted, premarital carrier screening and community-based education programs could play a critical role. Consider discussing the feasibility of partnerships with local religious and community leaders, who are often central figures in decision-making. Examples exist in other communities (e.g., faith-based premarital genetic counseling programs).

Discussion – Technical Clarification

Referenced text: discussion of non-invasive prenatal diagnosis.

Suggested revision: The authors should clarify whether cell-free fetal DNA testing for SCD is available in Kaduna or elsewhere in Nigeria, and whether cost or infrastructure barriers limit its use. This would give readers a realistic view of PND implementation challenges.

Minor Editorial Suggestions

Ensure consistency in numeration: the text reports 0.3% for undergoing PND, but 1/297 corresponds to $\sim 0.34\%$ —the number is correct but could be rounded more transparently. Consider adding a short sentence on how missing data, if any, were handled.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Sickle Cell Disease expert.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Author Response 05 Dec 2025

Rabi'at Muhammad Aliyu

Thank you for your insightful comments. METHODS None of the eligible mothers declined participation. The clinic attends to an average of 50 children with SCD per week RESULT

1. Grandmultiparous women in this study referred to women who have had five or more deliveries, and the term is now used consistently.
2. Tertiary education in this study refers to additional education beyond secondary school and includes diplomas, degrees, postgraduate

DISCUSSION

1. Point on religious leaders involvement have been expanded.
2. Clarification on cell free fetal DNA has been provided

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Report 08 October 2025

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.20230.r60590>

© 2025 Jordan L. This is an open access peer review report distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License](#), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Lori C Jordan

Vanderbilt University Medical Center, Nashville, Tennessee, USA

This seems like an important topic and excellent subject for investigation.
I have a few questions organized by section:

Methods:

The authors state: "After obtaining informed verbal consent, every eligible participant completed a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire to gather data on socio-demographic characteristics, awareness, attitude, and acceptability of prenatal diagnosis for SCD. The data collected was pseudo-anonymized. Recruitment took place from March to August 2023."

1. How many mothers declined to participate? If none, would reword the sentence to read: every eligible participant completed a structured interviewer-administered Questionnaire, after obtaining informed verbal consent, to gather data on socio-demographic characteristics...

2. How many children with SCD are followed in the Kaduna peds SCD clinics? One might think at least half of these children/families would have been approached within 6 months.

Results

Please define grand multip – from the manuscript I thought 3 pregnancies but from the table I thought it might be 5 pregnancies.

Please define "tertiary" education. Do the authors mean beyond high school? Some college

Discussion

The authors mention "there is need to strengthen other less expensive control measures in the countries like premarital/premarital counseling and testing and newborn screening" I agree! Could the authors say a bit more? Would it be acceptable to screen teens for SCD carrier status through a local mosque? Perhaps an Imam might communicate that it is best for 2 SCD carriers not to marry? Just thinking that if pregnancy termination isn't acceptable – testing prior to marriage might be best. (I believe this has been done in Jewish populations through synagogues for different severe conditions like Tay Sachs.)

Is cell-free DNA testing available for diagnosis in Kaduna? Is this available at many/most facilities in Nigeria? Is testing affordable?

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Yes

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: sickle cell disease - neurological complications

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Author Response 05 Dec 2025

Rabi'at Muhammad Aliyu

Thank you for your insightful comments. METHODS

1. It has been reworded. None of the eligible women declined participation in the study.
2. The Paediatric Haematology Clinic attends to an average of 50 children with sickle cell disease per week.

RESULTS

1. A grandmultipara referred in this study is a woman who has had five or more pregnancies that have been carried to at least 28 weeks of gestation.
2. Tertiary education in this study referred to an educational level higher than secondary school

DISCUSSION

1. The roles of premarital screening and religious leaders' involvement as control measures have been elaborated. In the Nigerian setting, awareness and acceptance of premarital screening for SCD are already relatively high,²¹ and studies have shown that many African individuals hold positive attitudes toward genetic counselling.²² Evidence from a multi-African country study by Munung et al. further suggests that adolescents may be an ideal target group for early sickle cell trait screening, given their openness to receiving genetic information before marriage decisions are made.¹¹ This indicates a valuable opportunity to expand low-cost control measures. In contexts where religious leaders play a central role in guiding social and marital decisions, their involvement could significantly enhance the uptake and acceptability of other control measures like premarital screening. Engaging community faith structures—for example, offering voluntary carrier testing through local mosques or churches—may be culturally appropriate and effective. Religious leaders often hold strong influence and have been shown to express supportive attitudes toward premarital SCD screening, and they could play a constructive role in communicating the health implications of two carriers marrying.²³
2. Cell-free fetal DNA testing in maternal serum is currently unavailable in Kaduna, and only a few centres offer the service nationwide, at prohibitively high costs.

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.